

Research on Theoretical Analysis and Optimization Path of Strategic Human Resource Management—Based on the perspective of Labor Economics

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Abstract: With the deepening development of economic globalization and the increasing intensity of social competition, the striving for and cultivation of human resources by economic entities has gradually become one of the inevitable choices for their survival and development, and the human resource management system that matches the needs of social development and the strategic objectives of enterprises has gradually become an important competitive advantage of enterprises. Therefore, each enterprise must take its own ability endowment as the foundation, fully understand the problems and needs of social and economic development, and use the high-quality solutions created by human resources as the tool to highly match the development trend of society, so as to promote the realization of the enterprise's economic and social benefits. Based on this, this paper discusses the application value of labor economics in strategic human resource management, introduces the basic content of strategic human resource management, and puts forward the effective landing strategy of strategic human resource management based on the perspective of labor economics.

Keywords: Strategic Human Resource Management; Labor Economics; Theoretical Analysis; Optimization Paths

1. Introduction

At the current stage, human resources have become the first strategic element to promote social development, playing an important role in supporting economic growth and promoting high-quality development. Many enterprises have also recognized the importance of human resource and begun to pay attention to the talent work. In this case, the concept, objectives, and models of human resource management of enterprises have undergone significant changes, gradually evolving from the previous personnel and professional function management model to the strategic human resource management model^[1]. The transformation of management objective from simple "control of labor costs and support on the business operation of other units" to the "highlight of the strategic position of talent leading development is also happening^[2]", so the effectiveness of human resources^[2], can be maximized and the

enterprise strategy can be guided". Looking at human resources management from the strategic level and integrating human resources management activities with mission, vision and strategic planning are the trend of enterprise practice in recent years, and also an important connotation of strategic human resources management.

Strategic human resource management has been regarded as an important resource base for enterprises to gain performance advantages and realize sustainable development^[3]. Existing theoretical studies have emphasized the importance of strategic human resources management from the construct and contingency views^[4], with the construct view emphasizing the fit between the internal components of human resources management from the internal consistency view^[5], and the contingency view considering the dynamic capabilities and resource base as an important path for strategic human resources management to influence performance^[6]. In addition, strategic human resources management is strongly oriented to corporate goals, and "matching" provides a way to realize the success of human resources management in serving corporate goals, thus becoming an important perspective in strategic human resources management research^[7]. Based on the matching view, scholars have identified the objects that human resources management needs to match (e.g., leadership^[8], external environment^[9]), and strategic human resources management integrates organizational and human resource strategies, enabling human resources management to understand the company's strategy and mission and to maintain consistent dynamics with them, which provides a wide range of technical support and organizational capability support for the achievement of strategic goals. By continuously adding value to human resources, it will make the company a more accessible and profitable organization and ultimately make it more competitive in a competitive environment. Therefore, it is important for companies to analyze the supply and demand of human resources based on labor economics to provide a basis for strategic human resource management.

2. The overview of Labor Economics

2.1. The Concept of Labor Economics

The essence of the proposal of labor economics is actually the scientific and effective combination of labor and the economic benefits generated through labor, because in economic activities, labor is its vital component, and it can also be said that without labor it is difficult to generate economic benefits. Labor as a special commodity, if its value can't be really exerted, it will affect the economic benefits to a great extent. At present, it is necessary to scientifically input the various elements of labor into the economic value, and through the labor supply needs to carry out an in-depth analysis to achieve the balance of the labor market, so as to produce the maximum economic benefits with the minimum labor input.

2.2. The application value of labor economics in strategic human resource management

In the current human resource management work, strategic human resource is an important task that needs to be concerned about, and requires that in human resource management must pay high

attention to the overall development strategy of the enterprise, and on this basis, human resource management is constantly optimized and adjusted, so as to make it more compatible with the development of the enterprise, to achieve the effective allocation of positions and improve the existing organizational structure, so as to achieve a win-win situation for both employees and enterprises. From the implementation of strategic human resources, the introduction of labor economics is very necessary, and its value is mainly reflected in:

On the one hand, it can effectively control the cost of human resource management. To a large extent, the application of labor economics in human resource management can effectively control the cost of human resource management, not only to save the expenditure of management funds, but also to avoid the problem of human cost waste. Strategic human resource management requires minimum input to obtain maximum output in management, and constantly optimize and improve the allocation of human resources, and if there is labor economics as a guide, it can help enterprises to effectively solve the situation of excess human resources, better improve the rational allocation of human resources, and improve the efficiency of management. At the same time, it can also provide an effective guarantee for enterprises to obtain more economic benefits.

On the other hand, improve the work efficiency. The good use of labor economics to human resource management work can maximize the efficiency of the staff to achieve the optimization of human resource management. There are many enterprises in the allocation of human resources are unreasonable, or in the talent incentives a great lack of these problems will largely affect the staff's work efficiency and effectiveness, so this is an issue that must be addressed in current human resource management. The effective application of labor economics to strategic human resource management can effectively remedy these problems and deficiencies. Analyzing the demand for human resources from the perspective of enterprise strategy not only improves the efficiency of human resource management, but also ensures the realization of the strategic objectives of the enterprise and gives full play to the maximum value and significance of strategic human resource management.

3. Theoretical analysis of strategic human resource management

Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) emerged in the 1980s and has been widely discussed and practiced in European, American, and Japanese enterprises. SHRM refers to a series of planned deployment and management behaviors of human resources for the purpose of enabling the enterprise to achieve its goals. It encompasses both the human resource activities that influence the behavior and commitment of individual enterprises in the process of formulating and implementing the strategic needs of the enterprise, as well as the integration of human resources at different functional levels to achieve the objectives of the enterprise. Strategic human resource management puts human resource management at a strategic height and focuses on the promotion of human resource management to the realization of organizational goals, which is a major breakthrough and continuation of the development of the traditional "simple personnel management ideas" and has been proved to be an important way for enterprises to obtain long-term sustainable competitive advantage. Compared with traditional human resource management, it has significant economic value.

3.1. Basic concepts of strategic human resources management

Strategic human resource management refers to the enterprise management based on strategic development goals from top to bottom of the human resources positioning, operation, evaluation, optimization, and improvement. It takes value creation and transmission as the core to synchronize human resources for maximum frequency collaboration and realizes the maximization of the enterprise strategic direction and path with the human resources management concept, configuration structure, compensation model, performance system and training system. Strategic human resource management requires enterprises to have a full understanding of the development needs of the social market and a deep insight into the organizational resources they need to complete the landing of the solutions. Thus, the action path, personnel scale, standard parameters and target results for human resources to realize the economic and social value of these resources are quantitatively, executably and evaluably designed, and the allocation of human resources is front-loaded rather than back-loaded to ultimately form a dynamic human resources system capable of responding, tracking, feeding back and optimizing and improving in accordance with the objectives in a timely and speedy manner^[10].

3.2. The basic characteristics of strategic human resource management

Strategic human resource management is a resource allocation system that matches the overall development strategy of the enterprise, which is based on the contribution of human resources to the survival and development of the enterprise, and the symbiotic relationship with the enterprise's business system, operation system, production system, supply system, and financial system, etc., which are equal and collaborative. Horizontally, top-down human resources configuration structure design, and even any other functional modules of the enterprise must be based on human resources allocation; vertically, the value of the enterprise's resources to explore and create, market demand insight and satisfaction, internal transaction costs and reduce the balance of organizational costs and profits cannot be separated from the scientific and leveraged design of human resources.

3.3. The difference between strategic human resource management and traditional personnel management

Modernized strategic human resource management and traditional personnel management has a big difference, so maximizing the efficiency of strategic human resources management by identifying the differences between the two. The traditional personnel management conforms to the functional refinement and division of labor in the industrialized economic system, which allocates people as material resources and positions them in a costly way. The basic method of treating people is to start from the cost of resources, the use of efficiency and productivity level, avoiding investing more resource costs in the field of recruitment, selection, appraisal, personnel mobility, compensation, welfare benefits and personnel records. Therefore, it is often treated as a service work without professionalism and technology and becomes a service provider for other functional departments of the enterprise. Modernized strategic human resource management system is as the core of the whole staff's symbiosis, co-creativity, and harmonious coexistence with science and technology, humanistic spirit, collaboration,

consensus, and profit growth. Based on the material and spiritual needs of human resources, it takes the core principle of stimulating and driving people's subjective initiative and the degree of social cooperation, focuses on the development of human resources' asset and value-added attributes, and relies on systematic, strategic, long-term, and technical management in the fields of planning, forecasting, development, performance, and training, etc. Therefore, it is a series of resource allocation design, motivation and action activities centering on how human resources can improve the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market, and it is a project-type, global and systematic human resources operation system aiming at the strategic development of the enterprise^[11].

3.4. Importance of strategic human resource management

Human resources are the main influencing factor for enterprise development and strategic plan development, and enterprises with abundant human resources are more competitive in the market. Various management activities such as resource development, business design and implementation of appropriate human resource management strategies can improve the competitive advantage of enterprises and manifest human rights. First, it enhances the execution of the enterprise. Production operations are the main activity of an enterprise to achieve its strategic objectives, which may be affected by employee competencies, corporate governance decisions, organizational culture, and other aspects. Therefore, when formulating and implementing strategies, enterprises will improve their corporate performance by developing strategic and systematic human resource management systems. Second, it enhances the core competitiveness of the firm. Strategic human capital is the source of creating the core competitive advantage of a firm, and the goal of human resource management is to enhance the core of the firm's competitiveness through acquisitions, and the maintenance of the firm's core competitiveness depends on the development and management of human resources. When the company's human resources become valuable, the company can enhance its human resource advantage through the development of strategic plan. Thirdly, it enables the company to obtain sustainable competitive advantage. The disadvantage of strategic human resource management is that it cannot gain competitive advantage in the short term, while the advantage is that it cannot be easily copied or imitated. Therefore, strategic human resource management emphasizes the concept of long-term management to create long-term competitive advantage for the company. Strategic human resource management focuses on implementing a range of human resource management activities in a systematic, strategic, and planned manner to encourage and support the achievement of goals and to continue to gain and maintain competitive advantage for the firm.

4. Challenges facing the landing of strategic human resources management in the new era

4.1. Inadequate human resource allocation

In order to control operating costs, some enterprises try to compress departments and positions as much as possible, and even require their employees to wear multiple jobs. Some employees in professional and technical positions spend a lot of energy on other work tasks and do not complete their own work to a high degree, the end result is that employees work inefficiently and perform poorly. In

addition, the human resource management of some enterprises lacks the basic concepts of labor economics and does not realize that the effective replacement of enterprise assets and human capital is an important method of controlling enterprise costs, which results in the wrong behavior of force resource allocation. For example, many enterprises in the development bottleneck, generally through layoffs to reduce corporate costs, this way to a certain extent can play a role in easing the enterprise out of difficulties, but in fact is not conducive to the long-term development of the enterprise. This kind of non-operational layoffs violates the principle of strategic human resource management, and the fundamental reason is that the enterprise's human resource planning is unreasonable.

4.2. Inadequate recruitment and training system

Recruitment is an important way for enterprises to obtain talents, and it is also an important content of strategic human resource management. However, in some enterprises, recruitment is random, usually when there is a job vacancy in the enterprise department or the demand for talents, only temporary recruitment, the lack of a complete recruitment plan, resume screening and interview process is too casual. The interview assessment process is missing, which ultimately leads to inefficient and ineffective recruitment, and it is difficult to recruit high-quality talents. In addition, the training system of some enterprises is too simple, unsystematic. The independence of each link is strong, but the connection is not close, and it pays little attention to the training needs of employees and the effectiveness of training. In the recruitment of new employees, the enterprise will generally carry out pre-employment training for employees. However, the content of the training is mainly the basic content such as the development history of the enterprise, rules and regulations, personal requirements instead of conducting specialized training on professional knowledge of the position, practical operation skills and related abilities. Training methods are also mostly lecture-based, which is the arrangement of training instructors on the staff of the top-down explanation. In this kind of employee training, it is difficult to attract the active participation of employees, did not allow employees to learn practical knowledge and work skills. It is difficult to effectively improve work efficiency and is not conducive to the achievement of the strategic objectives of the enterprise after training. Due to the lack of staff training system, the effect of corporate training is not ideal.

4.3. Inadequate Compensation and Benefit System

Reasonable compensation and benefits are both necessary to protect and enhance the life of employees, and also a reflection of the realization of their self-worth. However, in some enterprises, the lack of a sound compensation and benefits system has led to recruitment difficulties and high turnover rates. Compensation and welfare system is not sound in many aspects: firstly, the enterprise for the staff to issue benefits and the actual payment of employees do not match, the new employee probationary period is long, and the probationary period does not have "five insurance and one gold" and other welfare protection. Secondly, the salary model is unreasonable, such as "no responsibility base salary and no commission" salary model, and the salary adjustment is too arbitrary depending on the subjective judgment of the manager or human resources department. Thirdly, the salary level of the position is far below the average market standard. Due to the unsoundness of the enterprise's

remuneration and benefit system, it is not only unattractive to talents, but also difficult to retain general employees, and the remuneration below the market level is weakly attractive to social talents, which will adversely affect the efficiency and quality of the recruitment work.

4.4. Lack of systematic performance management

On the one hand, performance appraisal is treated as performance management. At present, due to the lack of in-depth understanding of performance management and performance appraisal, managers usually take the performance management appraisal system as a system of rewards and punishments for good or bad performance of employees and turn the performance appraisal system into the main management tool for punishing employees, rather than how to improve employee motivation through performance management. Performance management is a systematic process of work, through the setting of specific performance objectives and performance standards, and constantly guide employees to improve their work motivation. In addition, it is through the performance appraisal of the way to improve the ability of employees to enhance employee motivation to maximize the advantages of human resources and role. The ultimate goal of performance management is to improve the enthusiasm of employees and the operational efficiency of the enterprise. On the other hand, there is a lack of scientific performance index system. Performance evaluation is not based on the company's strategic perspective to design the indicator system, which cannot be analyzed between the indicators and the company's strategy to form a good relationship between the articulation. The lack of a rational system of performance appraisal indicators has led to structural contradictions within the enterprise and problems with the interface of work coordination between departments, as well as gaps between departments and posts. The inconsistency of indicators prevents the competitive system from working in changing the strategic intent of each layer. At the same time, insufficient knowledge of performance management and lack of performance management practices prevented company managers from accurately distinguishing between performance indicators and criteria.

4.5. Lack of strategic human resource management awareness

Even though enterprises have set up human resources departments, their functions cannot be changed from personnel management to human resources management, the level of professional human resources management is not high, and human resources departments can only be responsible for simple personnel activities. Due to the lack of awareness of the importance of human resource management in the relevant departments, the role of strategic human resource management cannot be fully realized. The development of enterprises cannot be separated from people, and talent is an important guarantee for the survival and development of enterprises, so the scientific management of human resources is very important. But at present many enterprises in China in human resource management often exists in the end of the behavior, the management of the staff did not pay enough attention and will focus management on performance improvement rather than staffing and management. As a result, the performance improvement is not supported by the corresponding talent assurance, which ultimately leads to the performance improvement effect is not obvious. In addition, some managers of the enterprise simply think that personnel management is the management of people,

so only the personnel management is limited to the recruitment, ignoring the importance of the training, assessment and compensation and other aspects. This behavior seriously affects the quality of human resources management, and hinders the communication between human resources management and labor economics.

5. The Optimization Path of Strategic Human Resource Management of Enterprises Based on the Support of Labor Economics

5.1. Optimize human resources allocation

With the rapid development of social and economic development, the development of enterprises is also facing different environments, and human resource management needs to be based on the actual situation of enterprise development to make effective adjustments. In order to better carry out the scientific configuration of human resources management and effective adjustment of work, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive optimization of the relevant personnel and organizational structure to ensure that it can better meet the distribution of human resources. When managing human resources based on the perspective of labor economics, it is only through the scientific configuration and optimization of the existing organizational structure and staff that we can effectively monitor the recruitment of talents and job allocation and promote the rapid development and utilization of human resources to the greatest extent possible. Enterprises can better stimulate the enthusiasm and enthusiasm of employees to work, give full play to their subjective initiative, create more substrate for the enterprise, and improve the enterprise's market competitiveness and social influence through scientific human resource management.

5.2. Formulate scientific recruitment plan and personnel training

Under the conditions of labor economics, strategic human resource management in the process of carrying out the work needs to be based on the actual needs of the company's positions to recruit the corresponding talent, the requirements must meet the recruitment conditions and the marginal cost of labor and marginal benefit of labor. After the arrival of the talent to the post in a timely manner for its pre-employment training, the enterprise based on the actual situation to develop training programs, which helps new employees to be able to have a clear understanding of the corporate culture and development goals in a relatively short period of time. Scientific training programs can help new employees to grow faster, which is the basic principle of labor economics in the investment of human capital, so as to provide reliable talent support for the healthy and long-term development of enterprises.

5.3. Optimize compensation and welfare system

Under the support of labor economics in the new era, enterprises must carry out scientific optimization and improvement of human resource management to achieve good development of enterprises, such as the improvement of the compensation system, the improvement of the incentive

assessment system and so on. In the formulation of the remuneration system, it must be a good performance mechanism and theoretical basis that the human resources department needs to be considered and paid attention to. Regardless of whether the level of remuneration is set at a high or low level, it needs to be established within the scope of the compensatory differences in labor economics, thus providing a more complete specification of the existing standards and requirements for performance pay in enterprises. In addition, the human resources department of the enterprise should also make use of the increased marginal cost, so that the marginal benefit generated by the production efficiency of the staff has a close relationship with the former, and finally to determine the efficiency of the enterprise.

5.4. Forecast labor market

In the process of strategic human resource management, not only should the enterprise internal human resources carry out scientific arrangements and management, but also need to give full consideration to the labor market situation. Enterprises make effective forecasts of the labor market for their own development, so as to optimize and improve their strategic human resource management. Because of the significant dynamics of the labor market, it is very difficult to predict the labor market. Especially when using the traditional forecasting methods, it often makes the forecast results not to meet the prediction goals and the poor accuracy, which directly leads to unsuitable strategies chosen in the process of human resource management, causing great economic losses to the organization. Therefore, the introduction and use of advanced technology is very important, such as cloud computing and big data technology^[12], which can help enterprises better carry out the prediction of the labor market, improve the accuracy of human resources management, and also adjust to changes in the labor market.

5.5. Innovative human resource management concept

Under the scientific guidance of labor economics, the first thing to do in order to achieve effective implementation of strategic human resource management is to change the traditional management concepts, the existing labor resources for the scientific use, and enterprise development strategy and human resource management to make effective combination, so as to fully ensure that the enterprise can obtain higher economic benefits. And on this basis, the enterprise management and human resources leaders should also pay high attention to it, and on the basis of labor economics to realize the development of human resources management, in-depth analysis of the current problems and deficiencies in human resources management, so as to take effective measures to be dealt with scientifically, to promote the continuous improvement and updating of human resources management work, and reflect the main stronger New meaning.

5.6. Improve the cognitive ability of employees in economics

If an enterprise wants to be bigger and stronger in the fierce market competition, it must have a strong team that is willing to work for the development of the enterprise. In the talent team of the

enterprise, many new forces are almost all fresh graduates of college students, they not only have strong enough working energy, but also have a certain degree of self-knowledge, so in the actual work can put forward some excellent suggestions, the development of the enterprise has a constant flow of power, they can be said to be the enterprise's mid-life force. Therefore, enterprises should vigorously train this group, so that they can have a clear understanding of labor economics, in-depth understanding of the corporate culture and development process, and through training can also improve their ability and level of work. Therefore, enterprises can invite relevant professional understanding to carry out training on labor economics, which can not only help employees in their work to constantly try the theory-based methods of corporate revenue collection and expenditure reduction, but also provide better services for the enterprise and create more value. For the better employees in the enterprise, they can be formed into a small team to promote their internal exchanges, which can continuously improve their knowledge of labor economics, and also enrich themselves and improve their own ability.

6. Conclusion

Talent is the first resource for enterprises to promote high-quality development and the primary driving force for creating a high level of competitiveness. No matter the product advantage, technological advantage or market advantage, it must come from the talent advantage. As the owner of talents, enterprises must correctly manage and operate human resources, so that human resources can exert the maximum value in the process of enterprise development. The construction of a strategic human resource management system is to fully implement the idea of "people-oriented" and "talent leading development", upgrade and optimize the selection and employment mechanism, incentive mechanism, evaluation mechanism, attract, train, use and live the talents needed by the enterprise, and support the landing of the enterprise strategy. In short, human resource management is crucial in the process of enterprise development. But the current human resource management work is also facing great difficulties, especially after the emergence of labor economics, which has begun to become an important direction for the development of strategic human resources. This requires human resource management personnel to be able to focus on the labor market and the enterprise's own situation to carry out the management, and constantly improve the scientific nature of personnel recruitment, configuration and performance management, and thus improve the economic efficiency of enterprises.

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